

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Diallel analysis at critical growth stages of rice

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We investigated the genetics of P tolerance across critical growth stages. IR28, IR29, and IR30 and local varieties Khonorullo, Mirikrak, Pawnbuh, and Ngoba were crossed in a diallel fashion without reciprocals.

The F₁ and parental lines were sown in P-deficient soil (available P = 5 ppm, pH = 5.0, soil:water = 2:5), in a randomized block design with three replications. Data on days to germination, flowering, maturity, and duration between flowering and maturity were analyzed following Griffing model 1, method 2.

Differences between the parental and the F₁ lines were significant (see table). Involvement of both additive and nonadditive gene actions was shown by a significant variance of general combining ability (gca) and specific combining ability (sca).

In days to germination, the parents were in two groups: 3 d (IR28, IR30, Khonorullo, and Pawnbuh) and 5 d (IR29, Mirikrak, and Ngoba). Earliness was dominant, but no hybrids were earlier than 3 d. In some crosses, the good general combiners Khonorullo, Mirikrak, and Ngoba, with significant positive gca effects, showed delayed germination. Other nonfixable components revealed less chance of isolating recombinants for early germination.

On the basis of early germination, the parental lines could be arranged as IR28 > IR30 > Mirikrak > Khonorullo > IR29 > Pawnbuh > Ngoba. Early × late crosses showed the dominance of earliness, supported by significant negative sca estimates. Late germination of early × early crosses and their significant positive sca estimates indicate the presence of nonallelic interaction.

Parents with significant gca effects were good combiners, revealing additive action. The gca of parental lines IR28, IR30, Khonorullo, and Mirikrak were in a negative direction.

Proportionately, higher nonfixable components for days to flowering and maturity indicate that improvement of the trait would require quite high selection pressure; however, they indicate little significance for genetic improvement of the character. ■

Estimates of gca and sca effects for duration of critical growth stages in diallel crosses.^a Port Blair, India.

	Days to germination	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Days from flowering to maturity
<i>Parent^b</i>				
IR28	-0.81**	-4.53**	-3.74**	0.74*
IR29	-0.03	1.24**	4.74**	3.42**
IR30	-0.85**	-2.53**	-2.34**	0.13
Khonorullo	0.19**	-0.95**	-3.67**	-2.53**
Mirikrak	0.60**	4.04**	-5.73*	-1.71**
Pawnbuh	-0.25**	1.40**	3.44**	2.01**
Ngoba	1.15**	9.40**	7.30**	-2.06**
Sji	0.07	0.29	0.28	0.37
S (gi - gi)	0.10	0.44	0.42	0.56
			<i>sca effect^c</i>	
	IR28/Khonorullo (-0.49*)	IR28/Khonorullo (-6.23**)	IR28/Mirikrak (-2.75**)	IR28/IR29 (-2.11*)
	IR28/Ngoba (-1.46**)	IR29/Mirikrak (-6.21**)	IR29/Pawnbuh (-4.70**)	IR28/Mirikrak (-2.28*)
	IR29/Mirikrak (-1.68**)	IR29/Pawnbuh (-4.34**)	IR29/Ngoba (-8.55**)	IR29/Khonorullo (-11.85**)
	IR29/Pawnbuh (-0.83**)	IR29/Ngoba (-7.34**)	IR30/Khonorullo (-9.51**)	IR30/Ngoba (-4.03**)
	IR29/Ngoba (-2.23**)	IR30/Khonorullo (-9.23**)	Mirikrak/Pawnbuh (-18.23**)	Khonorullo/Mirikrak (-3.01**)
	Khonorullo/Pawnbuh (-1.06**)	IR30/Pawnbuh (-6.88**)	Pawn/Ngoba (-6.95**)	Mirikrak/Pawnbuh (-6.85**)
	-	Khonorullo/Ngoba (-6.45**)	-	Pawnbuh/Ngoba (-8.20**)
	-	Mirikrak/Pawnbuh (-11.36**)	-	-
Sij	0.19	0.83	0.81	1.07

^a*, ** = significant at the 5% and 1% levels, respectively. ^bNgoba had the highest P uptake followed by Mirikrak, IR29, IR28, Khonorullo, Pawnbuh, and IR30. ^cOnly important combinations.

Inheritance of flag leaf fresh weight in rice

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Leaf fresh weight (FW) is one indicator of leaf water status. We studied the inheritance of the flag leaf FW in upland rice varieties IAC25, Acc. 36151, Qinai, and Qinnong 2 and lowland rice cultivars Heijiang 8, Hanjiu, N86-18, and Sachimnori. The F₁, F₂, F₃ and their parents were dry seeded in upland. Flag leaf FW dur-